

CHALLENGES OF BANDITRY AND KIDNAPING IN NIGERIA'S EDUCATIONAL SECTOR

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Abstract: This study examined the challenges of banditry and kidnapping in Nigeria's educational sector. A series of related studies was reviewed. This study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The study population comprised students, teachers, principals, and parents of selected secondary schools in Nigeria. One hundred (100) respondents were randomly selected. A simple random sampling technique was used to select study participants. A duly validated questionnaire was used to collect data. Data collection was analysed using descriptive statistics of frequency counts and simple percentages. Three research questions were raised to guide the study. The first finding in the study shows that incessant banditry operations affect the educational sector's teaching and learning process. The second finding reveals that banditry militates against the use of standard and expensive materials due to the fear of vandalism. Further, findings from the study reveal that banditry could deplete all necessary ideas and academic morale of pupils. This study also formulates some vital recommendations, such as the need for a national poverty eradication program, the need to resuscitate the national directorate of employment, the need for collective security arrangements by all levels of government, and quality education for the masses. Lastly, the FG should reorganise the country's intelligence system and build a capable and more proactive security apparatus in Nigeria.

Keywords: School, Banditry, Kidnaping, Security, and Education.

Introduction

Banditry in Nigeria, according to "Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary" (2000), is defined as acts of stealing and violence by bandits. "Cambridge International Dictionary of English" (1995) also defines a bandit as an armed thief, especially one belonging to a group that attacks people travelling through the countryside. Banditry in Nigeria is as old as the country itself, but its prevalence dates back to a little over two decades ago, when the country's military rule ended. Madama (2019) affirms: Since the return of democracy in Nigeria in 1999, the security system of the country was challenged by the rise of insurgency in different parts of the country, so much so that various militant groups emerged in the Niger Delta Region and Boko Haram in the North East. Very recently, there has been the emergence of armed banditry with its attendant crimes (kidnapping, culpable homicide and cattle rustling) in the Northwest region. The Nigerian academia has started researching the causes and prevention of banditry in Nigeria to achieve peace and order in our society. Egwu (2016) considers the political economy of rural banditry; Momale (2016) considers the changing methods of animal husbandry and rural banditry; and Oluyemi-Kusa Salihu (2016) investigates the effects of armed banditry on the livelihood and security of rural women.

Many scholars have also investigated cattle rustling and armed banditry. Olaniyan and Shehu (2016) and Rufai (2018). This researcher thinks that scholars have not been paying adequate attention to one form of banditry that has been ravaging Nigerian society in recent times, i.e., trafficking in persons. This heinous crime against humanity deserves the attention of all, especially humanists and educationists, which explains why this study focuses on this banditry paradigm.

Security issues are global issues that must be addressed to establish a climate conducive to socioeconomic progress. Insecurity not only endangers residents' lives and property but also halts a country's overall growth (Ekene, 2015; Haruna, 2016). Consequently, security and development are inextricably linked (Haruna, 2016; Nwanegbo and Odigbo, 2013; Chandler, 2007, as cited in Ewetan and Urhie, 2014). In most African countries, including Nigeria, security challenges remain a fundamental impediment to real socioeconomic progress. Various forms of violent insecurity have plagued Nigeria's political history, including civil war, election-related mayhem, riots and rallies, militancy, insurgency, and herdsmen/farmer confrontations. In recent times, Nigeria has experienced a significant setback in its educational sector, fuelled by the revival of several security challenges, including armed banditry, kidnapping, and insurgency, posing a substantial threat to the country's national security (Akanbi, 2015; Ephron, 2018). States such as Zamfara, Taraba, Adamawa, Katsina, Borno, Lagos, Kaduna, Niger, Rivers, and Kogi have already experienced the effects of these new security challenges.

According to Olufemi (2015), Nigerian governments have spent over 462 trillion dollars on national security in the last 5 years. The governments' efforts to halt the threat to avert a total breakdown of law and order appear to have failed to produce the expected beneficial outcome. The growth of extortionate bandit operations has added a new dimension to Nigeria's educational challenges. According to recent figures, over 2,295 teachers were killed and 19,000 others were displaced in Bornu, Yobe, and Adamawa States between 2009 and 2018, with an estimated 1,500 schools damaged since 2014 and over 1,280 casualties among teachers and students (Adesulu, 2019). Many of these occurrences went unreported by the national media, thereby distorting the genuine picture. However, oppression persisted even at the time of this investigation. These attacks impede effective teaching and learning, stifling the development of the nation.

For more than 15 years, Nigeria's violence on banditry and kidnapping, as well as the resultant humanitarian crises, have wreaked havoc on the lives of millions of children, women, and their families. With children under the age of 15 constituting almost 45% of the country's population, the burden on education and other sectors has increased. Thus, this study focuses on assessing the effect of banditry on Nigeria's educational system. In essence, this study examines the effects of banditry on educational progress in Nigeria. Banditry and kidnapping are quickly reaching alarming levels in Nigeria, to the point where they constitute a severe security danger not only to the country's educational system but also to other parts of the economy. This threat affects not only the educational system but also other parts of the economy.

The extent to which bandits operate within Nigeria has resulted in the dislocation of students enrolled in schools, a wave of kidnappings, the mutilation of people, the loss of lives, population displacements, the loss of cattle, and the disruption of socioeconomic activities in general. It has also contributed to the creation of an uncertain and comatose atmosphere throughout the country. Both the Nigerian government and its people are becoming increasingly concerned about the situation. Therefore, this study also investigates the repercussions of banditry on the educational growth of the nation.

In contrast, education is crucial to any society's development. According to Freire (1970), education is a major weapon of social change and should not be neglected by any human society that craves development in all ramifications of the word. The Nigerian government recognises the importance of education to the overall growth of the nation and "as an instrument for effecting national development" to the extent that Nigeria's philosophy of education is based on the following set of beliefs: Education is an instrument for national development and social

change. It is vital for the promotion of a progressive and united Nigeria. It maximises the creative potential and skills of the individual for self-fulfilment and general development of the society. Education is compulsory and a right of every Nigerian, irrespective of gender, social status, religion, complexion, ethnic background, and any other individual challenges. Education is to be qualitative, comprehensive, functional, and relevant to the needs of the society (FGN, 2004).

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Quality education also promotes the spirit of nationalism and patriotism among youth. Through education, it has been discovered that youths develop positive attitudes of togetherness, comradeship, and cooperation toward the entire nation. According to UNESCO (2008), "No development can be possible without humans, and no humans can reach development without quality education." In light of this, Anadi (2008) opined that for a nation to be developed and secured, there must be a considerable proportion of trained educated citizens in that nation not only to act as doctors, engineers, teachers, agriculturists, and scientists but also to create a new class that is sufficiently large and strong to establish its own values of justice, security, selection on merit, flexibility, empiricism, and efficiency. For this to be realised, our education system (primary, secondary, and tertiary levels) must be practical and functional. Therefore, quality education is the primary agent of national security and development for bringing society's vision into reality. "For example, if the militants, Boko Haram, armed robberies, and kidnapers were properly nurtured with quality formal, informal, and indigenous education from the grassroots level, all these security threats/challenges, such as terrorism, riots/civil unrest, demonstrations, intolerance, cult-related criminal acts, religious intolerance, arm robbery, intra- and inter-ethnic strife, drug trafficking, human trafficking, kidnaping, hijacks, and many other vices threatening lives and properties would not have been in existence" (Osakwe, 2013).

Statement of the problem

In recent years, many children have been unable to attend school because of the fear of bandits and thugs. Even when children enrol in schools, many do not complete the basic cycle. According to current data, 30% of children drop out of elementary school and just 54% transition to junior secondary schools. The reasons for this poor completion rate include the Boko Haram insurgency, banditry, and underage labour. On February 29, 2016, Babington Macaulay Junior Seminary, a school on the outskirts of Lagos, was plunged into pandemonium when some of its students were arrested. It was around 8 pm when the pupils of the school were busy studying for their examinations, that a team of 12 armed men struck and kidnapped three school girls. The internationally well-publicised incidence of school kidnapping has given a new dimension to Nigeria's security dilemma, as many secondary school attacks have been recorded. There were reports of kidnappings of instructors and students (Lagos Junior Model College, Igbonla) (Lagos Junior Model College, Igbonla) There were additional reports of students and their teachers being killed. School assemblies are shamelessly detonated, killing many (Yobe school assault), while school buildings are burned down, which undermines teaching and learning. Five secondary school teachers were taken from a school in Rivers State at gunpoint, which left the residents in

absolute panic and worry. There were also recorded incidents of religious-induced crises that affected schools. (Mission secondary schools located in the Nasarawa district of Jos were attacked by bandits and many others. Hence, this study focuses on critically assessing the influence of banditry on Nigeria's educational system.

Purpose of the study

The primary aim of this study is to critically examine the effect of banditry on Nigeria's educational system.

1. Investigate whether banditry operations have affected educational teaching and learning in Nigeria.
2. Investigate whether banditry has affected the availability of educational infrastructure in Nigeria.
3. Investigate whether banditry has affected the academic performance of students in Nigeria.

Research Question

This study answers the following questions:

- 1) How does banditry affect educational teaching and learning in Nigeria?
- 2) Has banditry affected the availability of Nigeria's educational infrastructure?
- 3) Does Banditry Affect Academic Performance in Nigeria?

Significance of this study

This study vets the effect of banditry threats on Nigeria's educational system. Hence, the study will unveil the various ways in which banditry has affected education in Nigeria, ranging from its effect on teaching and learning, the educational calendar, children's enrolment in schools, and the availability of educational infrastructure. The study will therefore be relevant to the Nigerian federal government, state governments, educational sector stakeholders, teachers, and the public, as the issue of insecurity has raised public concern. The above entities will learn a lot from the findings, and the recommendations in this study will be considered useful and applicable to help curtail the menace of banditry in the country. Finally, this study will add to the existing literature on the topic under concern.

Scope of the study

This study investigates the effect of banditry operations on educational teaching and learning in Nigeria, students' academic performance in Nigeria, and the availability of educational infrastructure in Nigeria. Therefore, this study will be limited to four selected secondary schools in Nigeria.

Methodology

The method and procedure for gathering and analysing data used for this study were clarified. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design on the challenges of banditry and kidnapping in Nigerian education. The study was conducted in the Akoko South-West local government area of Ondo State. The study population was public secondary schools in the Akoko South-West local government area of Ondo State. The total number of public secondary schools in Akoko South-West is sixteen, with a staff strength of 436 teachers (including principals), and the total number of students registered is 6700 students (Akoko Southwest Education Board record 2017). A simple random sampling technique was used to select teachers from four selected secondary schools in the Akoko Southwest local government area. Since the population was large, a total of 100 respondents were randomly selected from the selected secondary schools, which is 34.4% of the total population.

One set of self-structured questionnaires was designed for assessing challenges of banditry and kidnapping in Nigeria's educational sector (ACBKNES). The respondents are principals and teachers. The questionnaire has two sections. Section A sought data on respondents' demographic characteristics, whereas Section B looked at items related to the assessment of the challenges of banditry and kidnapping in Nigeria's educational sector.

Validation of the instrument

Before administering the questionnaire, the questionnaire was validated by Senior Lecturers and two other experts from the Department of Measurement and Evaluation, who determined the face and content validity of the instrument.

The reliability of the instrument

Trial testing (pilot study) was conducted using 15 respondents (five principals and ten teachers) from Akoko Southwest Local Government Area of Ondo State to determine the internal consistency of the instrument. The cumulative percentage was used to determine the items’ internal consistency. Reliability indexes of 60 and 70 were obtained for each cluster. The overall reliability index was 65, indicating the reliability of the instrument.

The researcher and two trained research assistants administered the questionnaire personally in the selected schools. This ensured that all the respondents were educated, the questionnaire was administered, and they made a return after filling the questionnaire. A brief introductory letter was written to ensure that the respondent filled in the appropriate information.

The sample frequency count and percentage were used in the process of analysing the data in this work. For the analysis, a Likert scale was used.

Findings:

What is the effect of banditry on educational teaching and learning in Nigeria?

Research Question One: To what extent does banditry affect teaching and learning processes in Nigeria?

Table 1

S/N	STATEMENTS	strongly agree	agree	disagree	strongly disagree	x	SD.
1.	Incessant banditry operation affects The teaching and learning process	50 50.0%	36 36.0%	10 10.0%	4 4.0%	3.56	.65
2.	Banditry affects punctuality of students in various learning locations of learning.	31 31.0%	54 54.0%	5 5.0%	12 12.0%	3.24	4.2
3.	Banditry often affects quality Of learning	32 32.0%	22 22.0%	42 22.0%	4 4.0%	3.49	.50
4.	Banditry operations against the standard mode of teaching	19 19.0%	59 59.0%	13 13.0%	9 9.0%	3.42	.49
5.	Banditry leads to poor implementation of educational programs	79 79.0%	15 15.0%	5 5.0%	1 1.0%	2.97	.38

Source: Field Survey of 2025

Research question one revealed the extent to which banditry affects the teaching and learning process. This finding was substantiated by the findings of the qualitative data, where most respondents were of the view that banditry affects the punctuality of students in various places of learning, affects the quality of learning, and militates against the implementation of the standard mode of teaching. The result of the findings is in line with Narmada (2019), who affirms that since the return of democracy in Nigeria in 1999, the security system of the

country has been challenged by the rise of security threats in different parts of the country, such that militant groups in the Niger Delta, secessionist (IPOB) in the South-East, and Boko Haram in the northern part of the country have emerged.

Has banditry affected the availability of Nigeria's educational infrastructure?

Research Question Two: To what extent does banditry affect the availability of Nigeria's educational infrastructure?

Table: 2

S/N	STATEMENTS	strongly agree	agree	disagree	strongly disagree	<i>x</i>	SD
		No %	No %	No %	No %		
6.	Banditry militates against provision of High-technology learning devices Fear of vandalism	57 57.0%	21 21.0%	7 7.0%	5 5.0%	3.68	.46
7.	Incessant banditry operations aid poor standard of the learning materials	38 38.0%	29 29.0%	17 17.0%	16 16.0%	3.57	.49
8.	Banditry militate against usage of Standard and expensive materials Fear of vandalism	34 34.0%	55 55.0%	10 10.0%	5 5.0%	3.26	.64
9.	Conditions of educational facilities are not secured	45 45.0%	33 33.0%	12 12.0%	10 10.0%	3.43	.70
10.							
11.	Banditry aids lack of trust on Security apparatus	33 33.0%	47 47.0%	10 10.0%	5 5.0%	4.68	6.80

Source: Field Survey of 2025

Research question two revealed that banditry affects the availability of Nigeria's educational infrastructure. The findings also revealed that 326 (81.5%) of the respondents agreed that incessant banditry operations aid poor standards of learning materials, while only 74 (18.5%) of the respondents agreed that banditry militates against the provision of high-technology learning devices through the fear of vandalism, which is one of the vices in the study area. In line with the findings of the study, Adeparusi (2021) asserted that the northern states, particularly the northeastern region of Nigeria, have suffered more serious violence due to terrorism and banditry. In fact, Zamfara State is one of the poorest states in Nigeria and is at the centre of banditry and terrorism. The poor state leads the table of violent insurgency, with over 500 reported killings in five months, that is, between July and November 2021. Cases of banditry are seen in Zamfara, Kaduna, and Katsina States to the extent that their governors, Abdul Azeez Abubakar and Aminu Masari, publicly declared that their states are under siege and that they are fed up (Daudu, 2019).

Does Banditry Affect Academic Performance in Nigeria?

Table: 3

S/N	STATEMENTS	strongly agree		disagree		strongly disagree		x	SD		
		No	%	No	%	No	%				
12.	Incessant banditry can cause poor educational output in students academics	47	47.0%	31	31.0%	7	7.0%	5	5.0%	3.68	.46
13.	Incessant banditry can cause poor performance in the students' internal and external examinations	58	58.0%	25	25.0%	14	14.0%	3	3.0%	3.57	.49
14.	Incessant banditry affects optimum The educational output of the society at large	34	34.0%	55	55.0%	10	10.0%	5	5.0%	3.26	.64
15.	Incessant banditry affects education National administrators remain committed to the implementation of An academic exercise that would aid student performance	45	45.0%	33	33.0%	12	12.0%	10	10.0%	3.43	.70
16.	Incessant banditry affects student performance by effectively frustrating and efficient use of the budgeted a fund that would aid students Demic performance.	61	61.0%	22	22.0%	10	10.0%	7	7.0%	4.68	.80

Source: Field Survey of 2025

Research question three showed the extent to which banditry affects the academic performance of students. It reveals that incessant banditry can cause poor educational output in student academic performance, can cause poor performance in students' internal and external examinations, and incessant banditry affects a given society's optimum educational output. In addition, the study reveals that incessant banditry affects educational administrators' commitment to the implementation of academic exercises that would aid student performance. The study generally reveals that when a student studies in an environment that is characterised by banditry, the student may suffer socially, mentally and emotionally, and it makes sense hypothetically to state that all these are likely to affect not only his behaviour and psychosocial adjustment but also academic advancement. Omo-Ojuga (2007) and Ajegbesan (2010) observed that quality education addresses major domains that reflect diverse goals and audiences, including the promotion and improvements of basic education, re-orientation of existing educational policies and programs at all levels to address national security and sustainable development, development of public awareness, and provision of training and retraining, which should involve higher education. Therefore, education must be holistic, encompassing both qualitative and quantitative processes, including "relevant curriculum, availability of adequate human and non-human resources, and assessment of

educational programs and processes through proper supervision and evaluation of educational outcomes to ensure quality assurance, control, and national security” (Osakwe, 2013).

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the inability of security agencies to address the country’s security challenges has raised some critical questions regarding Nigeria’s preparedness to attain the desired political, social, and economic heights. It further poses serious threats to Nigeria’s unity and corporate existence as a sovereign state (FinIntell, 2013). Over the years, successive governments in Nigeria have adopted several measures aimed at addressing the challenges of insecurity and banditry in the country, ranging from carrot-and-stick measures to the use of outright force and periodic critical evaluation of the performance of security agencies. These security agencies include The National Security Agency (NSA), The National Intelligence Agency (NIA), The State Security Service (SSS), The Nigeria Police Force (NPF), The Nigeria Immigration Service (NIS), The Nigeria Customs Service (NCS), The National Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA), The Nigeria Security and Civil Défense Corps (NSCDC), and The Nigeria Army, comprising the Army, Air Force, and Navy.

the goals and objectives of a united Nigerian state, are to instil in the populace a sense of absolute loyalty to the fatherland, ensure and uphold leadership by example, and foster respect for constituted authority (Oloya and Egbule, 2016).

Lastly, there has been a proliferation of vigilante security outfits (both private and government-owned) in the states in a bid to yield to the call by citizens to adopt community policing to support the conventional security apparatuses. This comes against the backdrop of the refusal of successive governments in Nigeria to establish a State Police to complement the efforts of the Nigerian Police Force, which is controlled by the National government and which they reasoned lacks grassroots touch.

Recommendations

Based on the study findings, the following recommendations are made.

The Federal Government (FG) should formulate and effectively implement policies and programs capable of addressing the root causes of insecurity in Nigeria, such as high levels of illiteracy, poverty, unemployment, environmental degradation, dearth of infrastructural facilities, and uneven development.

1. The government should phase out the National Poverty Eradication Program (NAPEP) and establish a more viable and result-oriented agency or even radically declare a state of emergency in the country’s educational sector. We hope to be able to address the problem of mass illiteracy, which leads to abject poverty among a large population of Nigerians, particularly those residing in rural areas.

2. There is a need for a collective security arrangement by all levels of government in Nigeria: Federal, State, and Local governments. The current arrangement, in which security apparatuses are completely under the control of the central/federal government, needs to be looked into and rectified. This is where community policing comes into focus. This security configuration should produce a committee at the village, community, local, state, and federal levels with the responsibility of providing sensitive security information for security agencies in their areas of operation. This will ultimately assist in the identification of criminals, their sponsors, and hideouts in the country.

3. Lastly, the FG should reorganize the country’s intelligence system and build a capable and more proactive security apparatus in Nigeria. This will add more value in checking incessant bombings, robberies, kidnappings and violent crimes/crises perpetrated by criminals in the country.

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